

Managing Editor's Column

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Dear Readers:

This number 3 of volume 1 of J.UCS contains 5 papers that cover an extremely wide range of areas. It is the first time that we have included two award winning papers from a big international conference, something we will continue to do whenever appropriate. Both papers come from the ED-MEDIA '95 conference, the Annual World Conference on Educational Multi- and Hypermedia that takes place in Europe every three years, this time in Graz, Austria, June 17-21, 95. ED-MEDIA is a large conference with some 250 contributions that you may be interested to attend. If you want more information you can just send an email to our mail server edmedia@iicm.tu-graz.ac.at or note the URL <http://www.iicm.tu-graz.ac.at/Cedmedia>.

The two award winning papers are: "Bringing ITS to the Marketplace: A Successful Experiment in Minimalistic Design" (best student paper) and "Combining Concept Mapping and Adaptive Advice to Teach Reading Comprehension" (best paper). We congratulate the award winning author teams to their very nice papers and look forward to seeing them in Graz!

Of the three remaining papers the one on "Special Cases of Division" is also a novelty: it is the first paper that falls into the category "Survey of a particular special field".

The other two papers on the "Halting Probability Amplitude of Quantum Computers" and "Modular Range Reduction: A New Algorithm for Fast and Accurate Computation of the Elementary Functions" are two technical papers of a more theoretical nature.

I hope you like what you see... and are encouraged to submit papers yourself. Springer is following J.UCS quite closely, is reasonably happy with how things are going and has just agreed to advertise for J.UCS contributions. So, you should see more about J.UCS also in conventional media in the near future.

All the best till April 28, when the next number of J.UCS appears.

Yours sincerely,

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'H. Maurer', with a long horizontal flourish extending to the right.

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